

Impact of COVID-19 on Baiga Tribe: A Preliminary Study

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 came as a disaster for the whole world, and no one was left from facing its unfortunate consequences. The level of impact is different when it comes to the people living in rural areas and are still living in primitive life; the pandemic and sudden lockdown situation have led to a significant health threat to tribal people around the world. The tribal community already experiences poor access to healthcare, lacking essential services like clean water, sanitation, connectivity to main-city, awareness, education, etc. The tribal life is based on the community life of social gathering, and deforestation has a significant impact on traditional livelihood, which compelled them to eke out a livelihood as migrant laborers in different cities of the country. The main objective of this paper is to study the life of the Baiga tribe who fall under PVTGs during Covid-19 and the impact of lockdown on the livelihood of this vulnerable group who lives in Dhanpuri town under Burhar block of Shahdol district in Madhya Pradesh. Apart from analyzing the socio-economic effects of Covid 19, the paper endeavors to focus on the impact of the pandemic on Baiga tribe of the study area. The universe is a tribal area with 44.65% of the scheduled tribe population. The research design adopted is descriptive using qualitative and quantitative methods, including tools and techniques like observation, interview schedule, case studies, and FGD for collection and analysis of data. The paper's findings are that Covid -19 has a vast impact on the life and livelihood of the Baiga community.

Keywords: COVID Impact, Baiga Tribe

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I. INTRODUCTION

India ranks second in the list of countries by population, with one of the major populations of the tribal community, almost 1045.46 lakhs which are 8.6% as per the census 2011. The total population of scheduled tribes in India according

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to the ministry of tribal affairs is 104281034. 14.7 % of the total tribal population of India resides in Madhya Pradesh, where 476,008 is the population in the Shahdol district. Madhya Pradesh ranks first among the States/UTs in terms of the ST population as a proportion of the total population of the state. The tribal community is again divided into two categories, ST which stand for scheduled tribe and PVTG which stand for the primitive vulnerable tribal group. Baiga tribe is one of them – a community that comes under the vulnerable group and has the least level of development. Baiga is one of the primitive tribal groups of Madhya Pradesh, mainly found in the region of Maikal hills covering Amarkantak, Dindori, Mandla, Balaghat, and Baghelkhand of Madhya Pradesh. The major population of the Baiga tribe is found in Shahdol, Umaria, Singrauli, Mandla, Dindori, Anuppur, Sidhi, Balaghat, Kabir Dham. It has six major subgroups. Baiga tribes show many similarities with Hindu culture. The tribe's way of life has shifted from its traditional hunting and gathering existence to the one closer to the mainstream, due to improved communications and their touch with the outside community. Baiga people have a strong physique heightened with tangled hair, expertise in the art of personal ornamentation, and in the decoration of their house. It is a tragedy that weaving is taboo to them (Elwin, 1943). They are also called medicine men due to their immense knowledge of ethnomedicine – they treat almost every health-related issue in their community with their traditional medicinal practice and sometimes also by performing a different kind of magic practice, as magic plays an important role in their belief system – they connect magic with many aspects of their life. The person who performs magic is called as guniya. Baiga tribes who still practice their primitive culture and are socially, economically, and politically backward from the outside world are very much affected when something unusual happens. The spreading of any disease, is sometimes a curse for this community, for example the pandemic (covid19) which has ruined the economy and taken the life of several people even in well-developed countries, so we can imagine how much it has affected the backward community. The health status of tribal populations of Madhya Pradesh is very poor and worst for primitive tribes because of the isolation, and remoteness, and is largely unaffected by the developmental process going on in India (ICMR, 1998).

The pandemic Covid -19 hits harder when it comes to a country like India which is still in the developing phase. Three percent of the total cases in the country were from 177 tribal-dominated districts till June 2020 (Hindustan times), Group which is socially and economically not stable like a group which live in poverty or below the poverty line, and the tribal people who were not made to understand the situation well as they live far from mainstream, have to suffer a lot for maintaining their daily livelihood need during the lockdown phase.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

PVTG group of Odisha was at risk due to the spread of the virus Anthropologists and campaigners believe that if the virus spreads further into indigenous tribes, the authorities may find it difficult to halt it. Because many tribes live in small huts, containing and isolating the virus is extremely challenging (Mohanty, 2020).

The Coronavirus virus has infiltrated the Baiga tribe's village in Madhya Pradesh, endangering the future of one of the world's most endangered

indigenous communities. They have very little immunity to viruses and novel pathogens (Naveen, 2021). According to the authority, it's the migrant who are returning to their hometown carrying the virus with them, normally Baiga People don't live in their homes but in the last few years they are moving to other states or cities for doing work as daily wage laborers (Chaurasiya, 2009). People who are still untouched by the rail trains even in the 21st century, completely connected to nature (and so called as Baiga or nature's son) like Bhumia Baiga and Bharotiya Baiga (sub-castes of Baiga), are the ones still practicing all their cultural practices and have the least interest to change, tattoo their whole body starting from the forehead as their identity and are well trained in hunting animals. Tattoos on the body of Baiga people have a special cultural meaning that can be seen in both males and females. Different tattoo designs are created for various purposes and at various stages of life, and women often view tattoos as fashion accessories. Body inking is a symbol of their culture that is also linked to their religious beliefs, social standing, and health care needs. In addition to protecting individuals from various natural disasters, tattoos offer therapeutic benefits that can be used to treat common illnesses and arouse sexual urges (Mohanta, 2015).

The Coronavirus virus has infiltrated the Baiga tribal settlements in Madhya Pradesh and poses a threat to the survival of one of the world's most endangered indigenous groups (Tomar, 2021). According to sources, they have essentially no protection against this virus, even though there are also cases where tribal people deny taking vaccination shots. There are different reasons for the same. Vaccination resisting behavior was quite common in tribal communities and convincing them was harder. The main reasons are that S have a belief that they have immunity to fight this virus and the tattoos in their body are their strength, they trust their natural herbs, the liquor they make of Mahua is their energy booster and also believe that gods will cure them.

The Sabar tribal community was affected severely in terms of life and livelihood, and their major economic activity – collecting mahua flowers and Sal leaves was also hit badly (The New India Express, 2020)

The lockdown has hurt the tribal economy in addition to the spread of COVID-19 among tribal youngsters. The tribal people in India had to deal with heavy loss of income, restrictions on the collection and sale of minor forest products, living in remote areas, lack of doctors and healthcare workers, lack of awareness, reliance on herbal and forest-based medicine, and the implementation of projects for forest acquisition without informing the village council.

Health status of Baiga village

- Severely malnourished pre-school children are found because milk is not available
- Drinking water availability is there but the content has high fluoride
- The consumption of calcium, thiamin, riboflavin, iron and other micro-nutrients is lower among Baiga
- Sickle cell anemia is the major morbid condition and goiter is common.
- Malaria cases are highly reported
- The use of medicinal plants is found to a larger extent
- They depend on primary clinics as access to PHC and SHC is difficult
- Cases of anemia and RCH among the women are found (Debnath, 2014)

Figure-1:

Figure-2: Dist

III. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this study is to assess the impact of the COVID-19 lockdown on the community of the Dhanpuri area in the country:

- To investigate the level of awareness in the community.
- To understand the change in the socio-economic status of the community.
- To find the role of government in the community.

IV. DATA AND METHODS

The present study is based on a cross-sectional study. The study area is Dhanpuri. The study area consists of 70 households in the area.